

**COMPENDIUM OF BENEFICIAL HERBS IN APASMAARA - A
CRITICAL APPRAISAL****Dr. Pushpa Hebbal*¹, Dr. Mrinal N. Rudragoudar²**

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Dravyaguna, SMVV'S RKM Ayurved Medical College and Hospital, Vijayapura, Karnataka.

²Associate Professor, Dept. of Kriya Sharir, SMVV'S RKM Ayurved Medical College and Hospital, Vijayapura, Karnataka.

Article Received on 15 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 05 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 16 Feb. 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18658320>

Corresponding Author*Dr. Pushpa Hebbal**

Assistant Professor, Dept. of
Dravyaguna, SMVV'S RKM
Ayurved Medical College and
Hospital, Vijayapura, Karnataka.

How to cite this Article: Mr. Dr. Pushpa Hebbal*¹, Dr. Mrinal N. Rudragoudar². (2026). Compendium of Beneficial Herbs In Apasmaara - A Critical Appraisal. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(4), 367-374. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Apasmara is equated with Epilepsy which is a chronic disorder characterized by recurrent seizures. The incidence of epilepsy in children ranges from 50-70/1,00,000. The prevalence of epilepsy in children ranges from 5.59-10/1000 in India. Collection, Critical analysis, Scientific study and documentation of medicinal herbs related to Apasmara becomes need of hour. Although Ayurveda has documented many herbs for seizure disorder there is a need of screening and analyzing these drugs with its beneficial herbs because all drugs may not be useful in all patients of epilepsy. Vaidya might go amiss in clinical practice due to improper selection of herbs. As a result there is a huge difference between the scenario shastra speaks off and the current scenario around us. This may be due to the difference in the method of study, teaching, research and practice. The presentation mainly focus

on proper way of selecting probable suitable herb in a particular Seizure disorder based on fundamental principles of Dravya Guna. Hence present work is selected for the critical analysis of the compendium of various drugs based on rasapanchaka and karma after screening from various Samhita's, Nighantu's, proven traditional practices and research articles. Hence an effort is made to collect the scattered references and probable mode of action of various herbs in seizure disorder which in turn will positively reflect the clinical practice of a vaidya.

KEYWORDS: Apasmara, herbs, Seizure disorder.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, an ancient system of medicine primarily concerned with preventive aspects of health for well-being through the concepts of positive physical and mental health. Management of mental disorders or psychological medicine was an area of specialization even during Charaka's time.

Sharirendriya satvaatma samyogo dhaari jeevitam.....ayurveda uchyate.

In recent years, the incidence of psychosomatic diseases has shown a tremendous increase throughout the world, especially in western affluent society, where most of psychological disorders are emerging as a greater and growing challenge before medical profession in that epilepsy is one among them. Many synthetic drugs because of many unwanted but unavoidable side effects have poor patient compliance. Therefore herbal treatment is being preferred over conventional treatments. Much attention and so scope is drawn towards herbal remedy of many brain disorders.

Our nation is blessed with rich heritage of traditional medicinal system and rich biodiversity to complement the herbal needs of treatment administered by these traditional medicinal system. Hence many single herbs and formulations are screened here from various references for effective management of apasmara.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

- ✘ To know beneficial herbs in apasmaara from scattered references from various samhita's, Nighantu's, traditional folklore practices and articles.
- ✘ It provides a better picture for selecting need based herb in a particular patient affected by Seizure based on fundamental principles of DravyaGuna.
- ✘ To resolve the problems facing related to aoushada prayoga in Apasmaara.
- ✘ To fulfill insufficiency of compilation of classical references to know the effective herbal drugs in apasmaara.

Epidemiology of Epilepsy

- ✘ 5% - 7% will have a seizure at sometime during their life.
- ✘ 1% - 2% of the population suffers from epilepsy.
- ✘ Peak age incidence: newborn, first decade, elderly.

- ✘ In only 50% is an etiology identifiable and 80% respond well to treatment.
- ✘ Chance of having a second seizure after an initial
- ✘ Unprovoked episode is 30%.
- ✘ Chance of remission from epilepsy in childhood is 80%.*

METHODOLOGY

- ✘ The scattered references are compiled to assess the Aushada prayoga in Apasmaara as multidimensional approach and special emphasize is given for effective herbs and herbal formulations.
- ✘ Hence the methodology followed here is compilation of references related to Apasmaara as a phalashriti of Ekamulika and formulations(yoga's) based on selected Nighantu's (BhavaPrakasha Nighantu, Dhanvantari Nighantu, Kaiyadeva Nighantu, Raja Nighantu, Madanapaala Nighantu, Shodala Nighantu.), Brihatrayees, Proved folklore herbal drugs and articles.

References of apasmaara chikitsa in different samhitas

Charaka Samhita ^[1]	Sushruta Samhita ^[2]
Cha.chi.9/38-kalyanaka ghrita	SU.UTT.61/23-Unmadokta chikitsa, purana sarpi, shigru katvangadi taila for abyanga.
Cha.chi.9/51-Lashunadi ghrita	SU.UTT.62/33-Grahokta chikitsa
Cha.chi.9/62-Hingvaadi Ghrita	SU.UTT.62/29-Phala ghrita
Cha.chi.9/72-Siddartakaadi churna	SU.UTT.62/26-Mahakalyanaka ghrita(apasmara,graha)
Cha.chi.10/23-Panchagavya ghrita	
Cha.chi.10/46-Kayastaadi varti	
Cha.chi.23/247-Amruta ghrita(apasmara, unmada, bhuta graha, krimi, skandagraha, sarvavisha hara)	

Astanga Hridaya ^[3]	Astanga Sangraha ^[4]
A.H.CHI 4/20-Daadhika ghrita	A.S.9/21-Lashunaadi purana ghrita
A.H.UT.7/18-Panchagavya ghrita	A.S.10/12-Sirishaaddi taila(apasmaaragraha unmada vishahara,medyam param)
A.H.UT.34/40-Shatavaryadi ghrita	A.S.UT.10/22-Vrishikalyaadi varti for anjana
A.H.CHI.14/106-Devadarvyadi kshaara agada	A.S.UT 40/55-vachaadi anjana
A.H.SU.20/2-Virechana nasya	A.S.UT.40/75-Sirishaadi Ghrita(apasmaraunmada bhutagraha, vishahara

A.H.SU.27/12-Siravyadha	A.S.UT.42/48-Lodradi varti(apasmara, graha, unmada, bhuta graha, jwara, visha)
A.H.UT.48/51-Agrya dravya Brahmi	A.S.UT.49/181-Rasayana vidhi-vruddadarvyadi rasayana(apasmara, graha, unmadahara and 600 yrs life)

Dravya's used in Apasmaara according to Nighantu's^[5,6,7,8,9,10]

DRAVYA	SHLOKA	REFERENCES
Vacha	अपस्मारकफोन्मादभूतजन्तवनिलान्दरेत्	Bha.Ni.haritakyaadi varga sloka 92
Dvipantara vacha	वातव्याधीनपस्मारमुन्मादं तनुवेदनाम् ।	Bha.Ni.Haritakyaadi varga shloka 93
vacha	अपस्मारकफोन्मादभूतशूलानिलाञ्जयेत् ।	Ma.Ni..Shuntyaadi varga shloka 39
Maha shraavani/mahamundi	क्षीपदारुच्यपस्मारप्लीहमेदोगुदार्तिहत्	Bha.Ni.Guduchyaadi varga 186 shloka
Shilajatu	अपस्मारं तथोन्मादं शोथकुष्ठोदरकृमीन्	Bha.Ni.dhatuupadhaatura sauparasaratna Uparatnavishaupavishadi varga.72 shloka
Hamsapaadi	भ्रान्त्यपस्मारदोषघ्नी विज्ञेया च रसायनी	Ra.Ni.Parpataadi vatga 113 shloka
Hastimada	केश्योऽपस्मारनाशनः ।	Ra.Ni.Pippalyaadi varga 248 shloka
mahashraavani	आमारुचिघ्न्यपस्मारगण्डक्षीपदनाशिनी	Dha.Ni.Guduchyaadi varga 181 shloka
Shraavani	गण्डापचीप्लीहमेदोऽपस्मारपाण्डुताः	Kai.Ni. oshadi varga 990 shloka
Vacha	हन्त्युन्मादमपस्मारं रक्षोजन्तुकफानिलान्	Kai.Ni.oshadi varga 1218 shloka
Bola	हन्त्यपस्मारकुष्ठार्शःभग्नस्वेदग्रहज्वरान्	Kai.Ni.Dhatu varga 85 shloka
Purana ghrita	अपस्मारग्रहोन्मादमूर्च्छालक्ष्मीविषकृमीन्	Kai.Ni. 4.Drava varga 285 shloka
Ghrita	अपस्मारग्रहोन्मादवतां शस्तं विशेषतः ।	Sho.Ni.Ghrita varga shloka 753

FOLKLORE MEDICINES

✘ Although many medicinal plants have been used in effective treatment /management of epilepsy in India only a few of Indian folk medicinal plant have been examined scientifically for their medicinal values. Some of the folklore medicines used frequently as antiepileptic remedies in indian folklore medicines are

Ashwaganda

Brahmi
 Vacha
 Palasha
 Jeeraka
 Amalaki
 Mandukaparni
 Sirisha
 Sarpagandha
 Tulasi
 Jatamansi
 Vana Tulasi
 Shigru And Other

MEDYA DRAVYA'S according to Nighantu's

Bha.pra.N	Ra.Ni	Kai.Ni
शुक्लजीरककृष्णजीरक भल्लातक बोल कालशाक जलगुण दुग्ध सद्यस्कनवनीत घृत गोमूत्र तिलतैल	निष्पावद्वय खदिर चीनक कर्पूरविशेष भूमिजगुगुलु सूर्यकान्तमणि गोमूत्र यव छागल	गुडूची दाडिम भल्लातक निर्गुण्डी बिम्बी शमी जीरकत्रय कैरोपितधान्य चतुर्विधजल दुग्ध सामान्यगुण) ऋतुविशेषेण दधि गुण गव्यतक्र गोमूत्र दिनचर्या

Dha.Ni	Ma.Ni	Sho.Ni
जलमुस्त (मुस्तविशेष परिप्लव बीजपूर गोदुग्ध जल गोमूत्र	जीरकत्रय स्थौण्यक बोल नि. हंसोदक दुग्ध यवतिक्तोद्भवतैल कृष्णव्रीह्यादिधान्य	गुडूच्यादिवर्गद्रव्यगुण चन्दनादिवर्गद्रव्यगुण करवीरादिवर्गद्रव्यगुण क्षीरवर्ग तैलवर्ग मधुवर्ग मूत्रवर्ग मांसवर्ग मिश्रकाध्याय

Srotas involved in the manifestation of Apasmara is

- ✘ Rasavaha
- ✘ Pranavaha

✘ Majjavaha

✘ Manovaha

Srotas	Ekamoolika prayoga	Yogas
Rasavaha srotas	kalinga Patola Katurohini Mishi Ajamoda Pippali	Babbularista, Manduravataka, Chyavan prasha avalehya Kushmanda Avalehya, Dhanyaka hima Dashamoolarista, Panchatiktaka ghrita Doshagna lepa, Dashanga lepa, Vishagna lepa Kutajarista, Vidangarista, Khadirarista Triphala Guggulu, MahaYogaraja Guggulu, Balaadi taila, Kalyaanaka ghrita Jadamansyaadi arka, Draksha avalehya Danti Haritaki, Dashamoola Haritaki Naarikela Khanda, Madhusnuhi Rasayana Manibhadra Guda, Shatavari Guda Shiva Gutika, Nimbadi kwatha PatoYogaraja Guggulu, Vatari Guggulu Simhanada Guggulu, Indukanta Ghrita
2) Praanavaha srotas	Swasahara mahakashaya of charaka • Shati • Puskara moola • Amla vetasa • Ela • Hingu • Agaru • Sarasa • Tamalaki • Jeevanti • Chandana • Haridra • Kantakari • Duralabha • Pippali • Karkata shringi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babbularista • Triphala choorna • Talisaadi churna • Dasha moola kwatha • Draksahaarista • Kankuma Nasya • Chandrodaya Varti • Pushpa varti • Rasa kriya • Darvyaadi rasakriya • Kanakaasava • Agastya Haritaki • Chyavana Prasha • Vasaavalehya • Amruta praasha ghrita • Kalyanaka Ghrita

According to Charaka, for Majjavaha srotas, Madhura(Yastimadhu) and Tikta dravya(Brahmi) used for treatment of Majja pradoshaja vikara.

Srotas	Ekamulika Prayoga
3)Majjavaha srotas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guduchi • Mustaka
srotas	Yogas
4)Manovaha srotas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chandanadi Lepa • Ashwagandhaarista • Brahma Rasayana

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

- ✘ From this literary research we can bring to a close thought that even there are so many herbs and yogas for apasmara is available. Although it is very difficult in selecting the effective drug in apasmara.
- ✘ Aoushada prayoga depends on many factors
 - Dosha bahulyata
 - Srotas involvement
 - Rakta dusti
 - Abhighataja
 - Sharirika and manasika dosha involvement.

Medicine should be given for long term and change of medicine according to the condition is necessary. Hence multi-dimensional approach is needed for effective treatment.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya Agnivesa virachita Charaka samhita elaborated by Charaka and redacted by Dridabala edited with 'Ayurveda deepika' and with Vidyotini hindi commentry of chakrapanidatta by Kashinath Shastri, introduction by by Acharya Priyavrit Sharma, Chaukamba Sanskrit pratistan Delhi.
2. Acharya Sushrutha virachita Sushrutha Samhita with Nibhandha sangraha commentry of Sri Dalhanacharya, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, edition, 2014.
3. Acharya Vagbhata virachita Astanga Hridaya with sarvangasundara and Ayurveda rasayana commentry of Arunadatta and Hemadri, Annoted by Dr. Anna Moreswar kunte and Ramchandra sastri Navre, edited by Pt. Hari sadasiva sastri paradakara, Chaukhamba sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi, Reprint edition, 2014.
4. Vrudda vagbhata virachita Astanga sangraha with Indu commentry, Chaukhambha sanskrit series, Varanasi.
5. Bhavamishra virachita bhaavaprakasha nighantu, translated by prof. K.R. Srikant murty, Reprint edition 2011, choukamba Krishnadas academy, varanasi, Haritakyaadi varga, Guduchyaadi varga, dhatuupadahatu ratna uparatna visha upavisha varga.
6. Madana paala virachita Madanapaala nighantu by Dr. J.L.N. Shastry forwarded by Dr.K. Raghunathan, edition 2010, chaukamba orientalia Varanasi.

7. Pandit Narahari virachita Raja nighantu, edited with ‘‘dravyaguna prakashika’ hindi commentary by Dr. Indradeo tripathi, 2nd edition 1998, Krishna das academy Varanasi.
8. Mahendra bhogik virachita Dhanvantari nighantu by acharya priyavrit sharma, edited by Dr.Guruprasad Sharma, edition 2012, chaukamba orientalia Varanasi.
9. Kaiyadeva virachita kaiyadeva nighantu written and edited by priyavrit Sharma and Guru Prasad Sharma, edition 2009, chaukamba orientalia Varanasi.
10. Acharya shodala virachita shodala nighantu, commented by prof. Dr. Gyanendra Pandey, edited by prof. R. Dwivedi, forwarded by Prof M.S. Baghela, edition 2011, Chaukamba Krishna Das academy Varansi.